

STEM CELL RESEARCH: WHAT DIMENSION IS IT?

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8331610

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).
srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.*

Maria José Beteste de Miranda

*PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).
mariajosebestete@yahoo.com.br.*

Evandro Carlos Salerno

*PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).
evandronorne@hotmail.com.*

“If there were 58 more wars on the scale of World War II, this would allow a time traveler to glimpse the possibility that, somewhere in the future, there would be scientists who mastered approximately 100% knowledge of the human brain and its behavioral variants. . There is only one detail for this to be true: Never having read Friedrich Nietzsche!” (SOUZA, 2023)

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of scientific research with stem cells, with the aim of clarifying how much progress has already been made in terms of knowledge on the subject and the possible results of the tests carried out. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it expands data that are already factual and also the discussion on possibilities that arise with each discovery. Its social relevance is presented in the condition of exposing to society the medical work that may improve the living conditions of individuals who suffer from disorders and pathologies, which are still considered to be incurable today. This is a bibliographical, descriptive, analytical and explanatory research, based on data. The great challenge that arises in relation to this subject is that, these studies demand longevity, high costs, deepening about the etiology of the diseases that most interest to find cure through the technique, solution of ethical and bioethical conflicts, pertinent legislation that supports such large-scale investigations. With each successful experiment, a whole range of publications, in various communication vehicles, are carried out, with the purpose of exalting the hope of hopeless patients and, with this, it is hoped to move public opinion, forcing congress to donate money to medical research involving treatment with stem cells and loosening biosafety laws related to

the manipulation of living organisms and research with human embryos and fetuses. The positive results so far found are from assays on in vitro cultured cells.

Keywords: Stem cell research. Stem cells. Bioethics. Biosecurity.

INTRODUCTION

Since the scientific definition of the hereditary transmission of particular characteristics from an individual to their descendants, through the laws of genetics, a feat that is due to the monk Gergor Mendel (1822-1884), science has been formulating thoughts on how to strengthen human genes to combat pathogenic agents that undermine its existence, cause illnesses and limit it to a condition of inferiority compared to other living beings, especially in relation to those that make up the animal kingdom.

The crossing of non-matching blood groups is a principle of *Physis*, only being observed and reproduced, on a directional scale, by humans. Among monkeys, as soon as the females of a certain group reach pubertal age, they are expelled to other clans, in order to mate with different individuals, thus avoiding inbreeding. If anthropoids are aware that this mixture of identical blood types can cause disasters and presuppose loss of power among members of the clan, this is ridiculous to say, because it would be anthropomorphism; However, what stands out with this epigraph is that concern about the health and vigor of the species is an instinctive issue, considering the case of animals and, unconsciously, considering the case of humans.

But, with the emergence of religion, man began to disregard this imperative of nature on his existence and applied endogamous marriages to his sons and daughters, in order to maintain the lineage of the cult and, hence, the concern with the maintenance of family assets was a matter of relatively short time.

However, with inbreeding, diseases and illnesses that were common to those groups multiplied and formed resistance; considering that, crossings between different lineages are intended to prevent the manifestation of pathogens in subsequent generations, making them more resistant and, until a certain disease manifests itself in some descendant, this is already quite far from the parents and progenitors and, is now treated as a rare case.

From the second half of the 20th Century onwards, in particular, with studies and advances in the field of Medicine and electrical development, with the creation of optical and electronic materials that made researchers stop looking into space, in search of knowledge -se-la-de-what, and began to look inside their own bodies, many things proved to be clarified and

capable of explanation, allowing hypotheses to be launched, as a solution mechanism for problems that still remain (almost) misunderstood by the scientists.

It is from there that the hypothesis begins to be put forward that the human organism has cells that, in the event of the loss of a specific organ or its failure, can act to regenerate the damaged region, replacing the destroyed cells with others in perfect condition. , allowing the patient to survive. These cells were called stem cells, which

They differ from other cells in the body because they have three characteristics: a) they are undifferentiated and non-specialized cells, b) capable of multiplying for long periods while remaining undifferentiated, so that a small number can give rise to a large population of similar cells, c) are capable of differentiating into specialized cells of a particular tissue (ZAGO and COVAS, 2004, p. 2).

Therefore, the question that challenges the entire scientific community is knowing how this cell, in particular, is transmuted into another, replacing the one that is damaged; therefore, causing complete wear and tear on the patient's immune system.

The results presented, as a rule, with isolated patients, are always seen with great skepticism and, not with enthusiasm, starting with the price, financial and human, which is coupled to them and, then, the lack of subsequent evaluative studies, which would prove, the proper effectiveness of clinical treatment with stem cells (or not) is not put in evidence.

Trying to hide behind evidence of medical achievements and advances achieved by the pharmaceutical industry, in improving the living conditions of the population in general, is a feat that has not proven efficient when it comes to results with the application of stem cells in combat to degenerative and aggressive diseases such as cancer.

STEM CELLS

Stem cells are types of blood cells that can differentiate into cells with very specialized functions, constituting, through this metamorphosis, different types of body tissues, which are necessary, due to any damage caused to them, whether due to the condition itself. senility, weakness due to a genetic condition, generally hereditary, or sequelae resulting from some mechanical trauma. In practical terms, it can be said that stem cells are cells that have the potential to restore damaged tissues and, thus, *help* in the treatment of diseases such as cancer, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease and degenerative and heart diseases (BRASIL, 2023).

The text above makes clear the meaning of *assistance* in the clinical-medical treatment of certain diseases, which are still considered to have a high impact on the living conditions of

patients and which can lead to early death. It is not yet a cure; It is an investigative method, from which it is expected to be able to determine the end of some diseases, for those who have the financial resources to cover the costs linked to the treatment.

Since the 1940s,

It was known that in the bone marrow there are undifferentiated cells that replace the mature blood cells that are being eliminated. These hematopoietic (= blood-forming) stem cells are rare (less than 1 in 10,000 marrow cells), and therefore their morphological identification has always been very difficult (ZAGO and COVAS, 2004, p. 2).

What is very clear is that everything that is available, in fact, so far, are hypotheses, not even being treated as theories, unless the word is taken in its semantic sense contemplation of god , that is, nothing more than a delusion, a revelation without any empirical scientific parameters; because, when taking it as a product of studies, the lack of empirical evidence and long-term analyzes awaken feelings of denial and doubt regarding the effectiveness of the applied treatment.

Another detail arises, which is the quantity of experimental treatments carried out. If, by chance, 10 (ten) patients underwent the procedure and all resulted in proven efficacy, given the number of individuals who were tested and failed, these would be considered mere miracles and not a product of medical efficacy, for the simple fact that, When a certain action is verified from the perspective of science, its results must be measured from the perspective of statistics, an instrument that gives validity to any experiment, and not from the presumption of efficiency, which is nothing more than a belief arising from common sense.

According to Zago and Covas (2004, p. 3),

Numerous experiments have provided evidence that stem cells from one tissue can differentiate into specialized cells from other tissues. For example, hematopoietic stem cells differentiating into cells of the neurological system, hepatic or cardiac or vascular cells. (...) It seems more likely that the phenomenon of plasticity will indeed be confirmed for some types of somatic stem cells, but in general it appears to be of restricted efficiency and to have limited practical medical applications. (...) The so-called mesenchymal stem cells obtained from bone marrow can differentiate in vitro into adipocytes (= fat cells), chondrocytes (= cartilage cells), osteoblasts (= bone cells), myocytes (= muscle cells). However, it should be noted that to date there are no pluripotent somatic stem cells that can be isolated from adult tissues using a practical and reproducible approach.

As much as theoretical studies show promise, empirical results reveal numerous obstacles to a powerful defense regarding treatment using stem cells. The difficulties and

obstacles imposed by Bioethics leave scientists and doctors even further away from proving (or not) the effectiveness of this type of treatment.

With each successful experiment, a whole range of publications, in different media outlets, are made, with the purpose of exalting the hope of hopeless patients and, with this, it is hoped to move public opinion, forcing congressmen to donate money to medical research involving stem cell treatments and loosening biosafety laws related to the manipulation of living organisms and research with human embryos and fetuses.

STUDIES ON THE APPLICATION OF STEM CELLS IN MEDICAL TREATMENT

Much effort has been made to advance studies on the application of stem cells in the clinical and medical treatment of patients with degenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's disease. Tests with *in vitro cells* are encouraging and, in this case, Specific to this disease, there is the possibility of using brain cells from aborted fetuses:

In cases of miscarriage, the fetal brain can be a source of cells that can be expanded in culture and used to treat adults. The use of fetal brain cells to treat Parkinson's disease has had relatively good success, although the amount of biological material to treat each patient (neural tissue from 5-6 aborted fetuses) has greatly limited this approach (ZAGO and COVAS, 2004, p. 3).

A limiting factor for the research itself is that the results, for the most part, so far come from experiments with *in vitro cells*, and it is not known exactly what could happen when subjecting human patients to treatments.

A soap opera on Rede Globo de Televisão *Laços de Família*, shown between June 5, 2000 and February 2, 2001, presented the character Helena (played by actress Vera Fischer) contracting a late pregnancy to save her daughter Camila (played by actress Carolina Dieckmann) from leukemia, with a transplant of stem cells obtained from the cord blood of her newborn sister.

Nothing more pathetic and moving; but, just as even the *poetic ars* is restricted to the empirical scientific knowledge of each era, the soap opera only showed the patient being saved through miraculous treatment; not whether they can enjoy a post-treatment life with dignity and well-being.

Proof of positive results in relation to the use of stem cells in combating these aforementioned evils and the consequent universalization of their application in health could

help many individuals to have dignified living conditions, with less suffering, for themselves and their families. .

However, for research to advance, a conglomerate of laws and ethical restrictions should be relaxed, and there could be all types of abuse against babies in the fetal stage, embryos and patients, who would resort to research as guinea pigs, given that this would become in a dangerous game of dice, where the justification would be that death is already certain for me...; any hope arising from treatment would be seen as a unique opportunity to end a long suffering, which only ends, for the patient, with death.

Zago and Covas (2004, p. 12) report that,

The clinical application of stem cells in neurology must be viewed with extreme caution to avoid discouraging or catastrophic results, as recently occurred with the transplantation of fetal mesencephalic neurons, which, in the beginning, was a therapy surrounded by euphoria and which was, progressively, being replaced by skepticism and finally disappointment, in view of the results revealed by double-blind studies that indicated the occurrence of clinical worsening in many patients.¹

Empirical research works are necessary, given that without them, it is not possible to achieve results that allow clinical professionals to work on solid foundations. However, the variables are imposing and difficult to determine *a priori* , which makes financiers remain skeptical.

BIOETHICAL DISCUSSIONS

Bioethics is the branch of ethics that arises from the development and advancement of medical research, involving studies with humans, animals, biotechnology, product testing, stem cells, cloning. Each nation sought, in its own way, to develop laws that regulate such studies and their practical application dimensions. “With the approval of the Biosafety Law, research with embryonic stem cells is now permitted in Brazil, however, the law establishes some restrictions for research with embryonic stem cells, such as:

[...] The embryos must be frozen for at least three years; they can only be used with the consent of the parents; The trade in embryos, nor their production and genetic manipulation, will not be permitted, and therapeutic cloning for research and reproductive purposes is prohibited. Therapies using stem cells are still in the research phase and can only be applied

¹For more details, see : OLANOW, C. *Transplantation for Parkinson's disease* : Pros, cons, and where do we go from here? *Mov Disord* 17, p. 515, 2002.

experimentally by researchers whose research project has been previously approved by the Research Ethics Committees (CEPs) (BRASIL, 2008, p 3).

These are questions that lie between the threshold of the continuity of expansion of empirical knowledge and the complete absence of critical sense, because determining time for an embryo, which is frozen, to be used, is the height of ridiculousness, because, in this time, it did not stop being an embryo, in which time did not pass for it, from the point of view of cellular maturation.

It is reiterated that the discussion should be based on the results achieved with patients undergoing treatment and how this could impact the lives of citizens: would this technology be available to everyone, without distinction? How much would someone be willing to pay for some women to abort their children, still in fetal condition, just to be free from a deadly disease that makes it impossible for them to have a dignified and happy existence?

The balance's pendulum is divided between two antagonistic situations, namely:

Technical, ethical and legal restrictions have greatly limited scientific advancement. On the other hand, the possibility of obtaining 'spectacular' results has encouraged several groups to rush attempts at practical applications in man before obtaining basic foundations and, at times, deviating from the painful path of very controlled experimentation to obtain answers. gradual (ZAGO and COVAS, 2004, pp. 8-9).

What the cited authors express is a genuine concern, in which researchers are euphoric about placing their names in the restricted list of scientific giants and, on the other hand, of patients boosted by a miraculous cure and who, for this, would spare no effort and nor any human consequences.

CONCLUSION

In this essay, we sought to discuss the issue of medical research involving stem cell transplantation, as a form of cure for degenerative neural, brain and heart diseases, among others, such as leukemia and diabetes.

The work of medical researchers Marco Zago and Dimas Covas was taken as a basis, in which they clearly present the concepts of stem cells and make a sober discussion about the ethical issue that involves this specific field.

What can be concluded, after discussing the topic, is that the bioethical standards that encompass the subject related to stem cell research are based on complex positions, ranging from concerns about how such studies will be conducted to manipulation of results, guided by

the sole intention of making gains for groups that can specialize in the subject and, thus, commodify human life, deciding who will live longer and better and condemning the rest to a miserable existence.

On the other hand, if the State and Congressmen leave the rules to the care of the scientists themselves, no one guarantees that there cannot be abuses of all forms, guided by the desire to arrive first (before their colleagues) at a result that promises a cure. definitive treatment for patients suffering from degenerative and/or aggressive diseases.

REFERENCES

BRAZIL. [Ministry of Health. Virtual Health Library. *What are stem cells*](https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/celulas-tronco) . Available at: <https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/celulas-tronco> . Accessed on 07/15/2023.

ZAGO, Marco A.; COVAS, Dimas T. *Stem cell research : scientific, ethical and social aspects*. São Paulo: Instituto Fernando Henrique Cardoso, 2004.